

Research

Correlation Between Renal Function Changes and Renal Damage in Term Asphyxia Neonates at Different Stages: Cross-Sectional Study

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Abstract: Objective: To investigate the correlation between changes in renal function and renal damage in term asphyxia neonates at different stages.

Methods: The cross-sectional study was conducted, the data of MIHS provincial hospital, Janakpur, Nepal from January 2020 to October 2021 were collected for this study. 100 full-term neonatal patients with asphyxia who were treated monthly were divided into severe asphyxia group and mild asphyxia group, each with 50 cases, and they all meet the clinical requirements of full-term asphyxia neonates bed diagnosis. SPSS 25.0 software was used for analysis, and the measurement data used mean $\pm$ standard deviation ($\bar{x} \pm s$) means, using t-test for comparison between groups; the numerical data were expressed, and the data were verified using χ^2 , $P > 0.05$, the difference is not statistically significant, $P < 0.05$, there is a difference between each group is statistically significant Statistical significance, $P < 0.01$, the difference is statistically significant.

Result: Among 100 patients, there were 45 cases of renal damage, 18 cases of mild asphyxia group of patients, 27 cases in the group of patients with severe asphyxia, neonatal asphyxia occurred after renal damage was 45%. Severe asphyxia group within 24h serum BUN was (3.83 ± 0.12) mmol / L, patients with mild asphyxia group (3.79 ± 0.17) mmol / L, with a larger difference between sex ($P < 0.05$). On the third day of severe asphyxia group serum BUN was (3.86 ± 0.19) mmol / L, patients with mild asphyxia group (3.76 ± 0.16) mmol / L, there was a significant difference between the differences ($P < 0.05$). Severe asphyxia group of patients with mild asphyxia group Cr, UA and serum β 2-MG at 24h, the first 3d, 7d in both the first there is a big difference, and the difference was statistically significant ($P < 0.05$).

Conclusion: Asphyxiated term newborns are prone to kidney damage, and the extent of damage and the patient's degree of asphyxia have close ties, showing a positive relationship. Serum BUN, Cr, UA, and 2-MG and other indicators can effectively detect the occurrence of newborn infants after asphyxia with a degree of renal damage, with a strong clinical significance worthy of promotion and use in clinical practice.

Keywords: Newborns; Asphyxia; renal damage

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Introduction

Asphyxia is a relatively common clinical symptom in newborns and leading cause of neonatal death. or an important factor of mental disability, according to survey statistics, suffocation has become an important disability factor for children under 5 years old, and asphyxia of new borns will Cause damage to multiple organs and tubes in the whole body, the most important one is the kidney and trachea, and the incidence rate has increased. Reach more than 50% [1]. Kidney injury after neonatal asphyxia did not appear more obvious clinical features, but kidney damage is reversible in the early stages and can progress if left untreated lead to renal insufficiency in patients, and even renal failure and dialysis [2]. Birth asphyxia is an eventuality having far reaching consequences in the neonatal period. Hypoxia and ischemia can cause damage to almost every tissue and organ in the body and various target organs involved. Renal insult is a recognized complication of birth asphyxia and carries a poor prognosis. Timely detection of renal dysfunction and appropriate management may favorably alter the prognosis in many neonates with birth asphyxia [3]. 100 cases of neonatal asphyxia admitted in MIHS provincial hospital, janakpur, Nepal from January 2020 to October 2021 the patient investigated the dynamic changes of renal function, and the findings are reported as follows:

Research Methodology

General information:

The cross-sectional study was conducted, the data of MIHS provincial hospital, janakpur, Nepal from January 2020 to October 2021 were collected for this study. 100 full-term neonatal patients with asphyxia who were treated monthly were divided into severe asphyxia group and mild asphyxia group, each with 50 cases, and they all meet the clinical requirements of full-term asphyxia neonates bed diagnosis. Among them, there were 23 male patients in the severe asphyxia group, and 27 female patients, the gestational age was 37-42 weeks, the average was (37±5) weeks, and the body weight was 2501~3900g, with an average of (2501±1399)g, and 20 cases with abnormal umbilical cord, There were 12 cases of amniotic fluid factor and 18 cases of pregnancy complications; male patients in the mild asphyxia group 21 cases, 29 female patients, gestational age ranged from 37.5 to 41.3 weeks, with an average of (37.5±3.8) weeks, body weight 2500-3880g, average (2500±1380) g, with 14 cases of abnormal umbilical cord, 17 cases of amniotic fluid factor, and 19 cases of pregnancy complications; 30 cases of healthy full-term newborns were selected as the control group, among them, the male patients There were 13 cases, 17 cases were female patients, the gestational age was 37.2-41.6 weeks, the average (37.2±4.4) weeks, body weight 2503-3891g, average (2503±1388)g. The general data of patients in the three groups, such as gender, age, course of disease, and primary disease, were compared between groups. Comparison, the difference was not statistically significant ($P > 0.05$), comparable.

Test methods:

All neonatal patients were treated within 24 h, 3d, and 7d after birth, draw 4ml of peripheral venous blood, place it in an anticoagulant tube, use Jaffe's colorimetric BUN (serum urea nitrogen), Cr (creatinine), UA (uric acid) and β 2-MG (microglobulin) and other indicators, using Beckman CX7 automatic production Chemical analyzer for effective detection.

Assessment criteria:

Assessment criteria for neonatal asphyxia degree

The diagnosis of neonatal asphyxia is mainly based on the Apgar scoring criteria, neonatal Patients with a score of (4 to 7) at 1 minute after birth are mild asphyxia, and patients with a score of 3 to 5 minutes Patients with a score of < 5 in the center are considered severe asphyxia.

Assessment criteria for neonatal renal impairment

Diagnostic criteria for renal damage after asphyxia in neonatal patients: serum BUN the normal value is (2.5-6.4) mmol/L, the normal value of Cr is (62-115) the normal values of μ mol/L and UA are (208-428) μ mol/L, β 2-MG the normal value

is (1-3) mg/L, and the above-mentioned indicators appear in patients during the diagnosis process. If an abnormality is marked, it is diagnosed as kidney damage.

Statistical method:

SPSS 25.0 software was used for analysis, and the measurement data used mean ± standard deviation(x ±s) means, using t-test for comparison between groups;the numerical data were expressed, and the data were verified using χ², P > 0.05, the difference is not statistically significant, P < 0.05, there is a difference between each group is statistically significant Statistical significance, P < 0.01, the difference is statistically significant.

Results and discussion

Comparison between groups of data

Among the 100 patients, there were 45 cases of renal impairment, and 18 cases were in the mild asphyxia group, 27 patients in the severe asphyxia group, after neonatal asphyxia the occurrence rate of renal damage was 45%, see Table 2. Serum BUN of patients in severe asphyxia group was (3.83±0.12) mmol/L within 24 hours, and the patients in the mild asphyxia group were (3.79±0.17) mmol/L, there was a big difference between the two (P <0.05), On the third day, the serum BUN of patients in the severe asphyxia group was (3.86±0.19) mmol/L, patients in the mild asphyxia group (3.76±0.16) mmol/L, there was a difference between the two difference was significant (P <0.05). Patients in severe asphyxia group and mild asphyxia group Cr, UA and serum β2-MG all exist in 24h, 3d and 7d. There was a large difference, and the difference was statistically significant (P <0.05), see Table 1.

Table 1 Comparison table of serum BUN and other index levels of neonatal patients in each group at different times

Group	BUN (mmol/L)			UA (μmol/L)		
	24h	3d	7d	24h	3d	7d
mild asphyxia group	3.79±0.17	3.76±0.16	3.75±0.19	273.33±13.59	275.25±15.59	274.10±11.21
Severe asphyxia group	3.83±0.12	3.86±0.19	3.76±0.20	274.23±9.87	281.51±12.45	275.20±10.66
healthy control group	3.79±0.11	3.75±0.12	3.69±0.20	270.27±15.26	247.4±12.19	270.02±12.56

Group	Cr (μmol/L)			β2-Mg(mg/L)		
	24h	3d	7d	24h	3d	7d
mild asphyxia group	67.15±8.28	77.47±11.88	72.09±11.29	2.81±0.13	2.88±0.15	2.81±0.12
Severe asphyxia group	72.10±10.77	86.19±16.29	79.20±25.27	2.88±0.19	2.95±0.18	2.86±0.19
healthy control group	69.29±5.77	74.66±15.50	72.62±5.41	1.82±0.29	2.82±0.09	2.76±0.12

Note: Compared with the mild asphyxia group, the severe asphyxia group, ΔP <0.05; ΔP <0.05 in the asphyxia group compared with the healthy control group

Table 2 The relationship between the degree of asphyxia and abnormal renal damage in neonatal patients

Group	number of case	abnormal kidney function	normal kidney function
mild asphyxia group	50	18 (36%)	32 (64%)
Severe asphyxia group	50	27 (54%)	23 (46%)

Note: Compared with severe asphyxia group kidney damage: $\chi^2=2.5859, \Delta P<0.05$.

Neonatal asphyxia is a relatively common complication in the neonatal period. Neonatal asphyxia mainly refers to a newborn who is not breathing or Hypoxic state in patients with respiratory depression [3]. Under normal circumstances, the child will have a fetal uterus Internal distress, suffocation already existed in utero, but the condition worsened after birth the continuation of the step has led to the death or disability of the child [4]. Asphyxiated newborns will Causes damage to multiple organs and tubes in the patient's body. In recent years, pediatricians according to clinical statistics, the rate of kidney damage after neonatal asphyxia has reached more than 50%. Currently neonatal asphyxia has become an important task of clinical treatment [5]. Neonatal asphyxia a hypoxic phenomenon ensues, which in turn triggers the patient's systemic hemodynamic medical disorders, the blood perfusion in each organ of the child will be reduced to varying degrees less [6]. When a newborn is asphyxiated, it will adversely affect the internal organs of the body. The same degree of impact, mild asphyxia can affect the child's non-living organs, such as the patient's kidneys and stomach, but the blood flow of vital organs such as the patient's brain and adrenal glands The amount is still in the normal state, or there is a slight decrease; severe apnea will Gradually reduces blood flow to the patient's vital organs. Therefore, when a neonatal patient after asphyxia, especially severe asphyxia, renal function damage is more serious [7]. The mechanism of kidney damage caused by neonatal asphyxia is relatively complicated. After asphyxia, it will inevitably lead to hypoxia in various internal organs and tissues of the body. and acidosis, but a series of stress reactions will also appear in the patient's body at the same time in response, the renin-angiotensin-aldosterone system will express abnormal excitement, Gradually lead to the vasoconstriction of various organs in the patient's body, and the renal blood flow gradually decreases. Insufficient renal perfusion occurs, which are the main factors leading to renal damage [8], Simultaneous stress and ischemia-reperfusion, the body of patients with neonatal asphyxia will a large number of inflammatory mediators and oxygen free radicals are produced, which gradually lead to systemic inflammatory response syndrome, which in turn leads to kidney damage, and even multiple organ failure. The clinical symptom of early renal damage is less urine output [9]. In clinical practice, it is generally believed that after the glomerular filtration rate of patients drops to more than 50%, Patients have abnormal levels of BUN, Cr and UA. But patients in the early When renal tubular damage occurs in the early stage, the urine output does not decrease any more, BUN, Cr and UA and other indicators have shown normal levels, so the above infectious indicators cannot be simply The standard is used as the basis for the evaluation of renal damage. 2-MG is mainly produced by lymphocytes, Belonging to a low molecular weight plasma protein, the synthesis and release of normal healthy people Velocity is constant and can freely flow through the glomerular capillaries filtered, but more than 99.9% will be reabsorbed by proximal renal tubules and resulting in decomposition [10]. When the patient's glomerular filtration rate gradually decreases, the serum β_2 -MB will gradually increase, which mainly shows that there is kidney damage in the patient's body harmful phenomenon. When the patient's renal tubular reabsorption is impaired, the patient's urine β_2 -MB levels were significantly increased [11,12]. In this investigation and study, The research done in MIHS provincial hospital, janakpur, Nepal from January 2020 to October 2021 of the 100 patients with neonatal asphyxia admitted for testing, 45 had renal damage 18 patients in the mild asphyxia group and 27 patients in the severe asphyxia group In patients, the rate of renal damage after neonatal asphyxia was 45%, and there were differences between the two groups. The difference in was statistically significant ($P < 0.05$). Serum of patients in severe asphyxia group BUN was (3.83 ± 0.12) mmol/L within 24 hours, and the mild asphyxia group was (3.79 ± 0.17) mmol/L, there was a big difference between the two ($P < 0.05$), On the third day, the serum BUN of patients in the severe asphyxia group was (3.86 ± 0.19) mmol/ L, patients in the mild asphyxia group (3.76 ± 0.16) mmol/L, there was a difference between the two The difference was significant ($P < 0.05$). Patients in severe asphyxia

group and mild asphyxia group Cr, UA and serum β 2-MG all exist in 24h, 3d and 7d There was a large difference, and the difference was statistically significant ($P < 0.05$).

Conclusion

In conclusion, full-term neonates who are asphyxiated within one minute after birth, renal damage is very easy to occur, and the degree of damage is closely related to the degree of asphyxia of the patient, and there is a positive correlation. neonatal patients indices such as BUN, Cr, UA and β 2-MG in serum can be effectively detected the degree of renal damage in children has important clinical significance and is worthy of clinical further use and promotion in bed.

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References

- [1] An Xuexia, Yin Aiyun, Chen Zhihua, etc. Serum TNF- α , IL-8, The role of IL-10 changes in renal injury[J]. Chinese General Medicine, 2012,12(08):67-90.
- [2] Lan Haiyan, Feng Chiguang, Gao Jiemei. Correlation between degree of asphyxia and renal blood flow and renal function[J]. Chinese Journal of Neonatology, 2008,11(05):65-98.
- [3] Fang Xiaoyan, Xu Hong, Feng Zhiming, et al. Analysis of early indicators of neonatal renal dysfunction[J]. Journal of Clinical Pediatrics, 2008,09(02):31-82.
- [4] Yang Zhiyun, Zhao Hongying. Clinical analysis of 42 cases of neonatal asphyxia with multiple organ dysfunction[J]. Clinical Medicine, 2001,11(09):12-34.
- [5] Li Ming, Wu Qiwu. Research progress on renal function damage after neonatal asphyxia[J]. Modern Medicine, 2010,12(28):89-102.
- [6] Akcan-Arikan A, Zappitelli M, Loftis LL, Washburn KK, Jefferson LS, Goldstein LS. Modified RIFLE criteria for critically ill children with acute kidney injury. *Kidney Int* 2007;71:1028–35.
- [7] Friedlich PS, Evans JR, Tulassay T, Seri I. Acute and chronic renal failure. In: Taush HW, Ballard RA, Gleason LA, eds. *Avery's Disease of the Newborn*, 8th edn. Philadelphia, PA: Elsevier, 2005;1298–1306.
- [8] Askenazi DJ, Ambalvanan N, Goldstein SL. Acute kidney injury in critically ill newborns: what do we know? What do we need to learn? *Pediatr Nephrol* 2009;24:265–74.
- [9] Askenazi DJ, Koralkar R, Parikh S, Deverajan P, Goldstein SL, Ambalvanan N. Biomarkers of acute kidney injury predict mortality in low birthweight infants (abstract). *Pediatr Nephrol* 2010;25:191.
- [11] Sheridan AM, Bonventre JV. Cell biology and molecular mechanisms of injury in ischemic acute renal failure. *Curr Opin Nephrol Hypertens* 2000;9:427–34.
- [12] Gupta BD, Sharma P, Bagla J, Parakh M, Soni JP. Renal failure in asphyxiated neonates. *Indian Pediatric* 2005;42:928–34.

